

METHODS OF OVERCOMING CULTURAL BARRIERS IN THE TRANSLATION OF UZBEK PROVERBS INTO ENGLISH

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Abstract:

In this article the linguistic and cultural difficulties in translating Uzbek proverbs into English are examined. Techniques for overcoming cultural barriers while maintaining national features are examined using linguistic and translation studies methodologies. The aim is to demonstrate ways to ensure cultural equivalence between the two languages.

Keywords:

Proverbs, translation challenges, cultural adaptation, cultural barriers, equivalence.

Language is a complex linguistic system that expresses the cognitive and cultural structure, worldview of a particular people. One of the deepest layers of this system is paremiological units, which learns proverbs, which are commonly used in folk oral literature and written sources. It is important to state that the linguistic analysis of proverbs and their translation into another language is not a practice of lexical units. This is, first of all, a complex translation problem of two different linguistic worldviews and semantic fields. Studying the features of extracting proverbs in Uzbek literature and the issue of editing the document into English, we witness that the translator faces not only a grammatical, but also a deep lexical-semantic and pragmatic obstacle [Salomov, 1983:45].

It is clear that the Uzbek language belongs to the Turkic language family, and its lexical formation contains hundreds of relations that conveys the national mentality, social relations and lifestyle of our people, which have been formed over the time. The English language, which belongs to the Indo-European language family, was formed on a different historical and linguistic-cultural basis. In linguistics, this situation is called interlingual asymmetry, and it is this factor that makes it difficult to find a complete and absolute equivalent of proverbs [Baker, 2018:21]. For example, when translating purely national words such as "*mahalla*", "*tandir*", "*chopon*", "*beshik*", which often occur in Uzbek proverbs, into English, the translator has to consider how to fill the lexical gaps in the text.

My observations show that the most serious mistake in translation is to translate a proverb word for word, putting it into syntactic patterns. Although such a translation fully complies with the grammatical rules of the English language, it loses its original pragmatic impact and semantic integrity. Uzbek analogies or metaphorical transfers may seem like a collection of illogical words to a Western reader. As P. Newmark stated in his theoretical views, when translating units of national character, a communicative approach should always prevail, that is, the translator should translate the purpose behind the text, not the linguistic word [Newmark, 1988:81].

Analysis 1: Partial Equivalence (Lexical-Semantic Asymmetry)

One of the most interesting and at the same time complex issues in translation studies is the study of the places where different people imagine the world and express it in different ways. We can clearly see this in the example of the proverb "*Ot aylanib qozig'ini topar*", which is widespread among our people. If we translate this paremiological unit into English literally as "*A horse wanders and finds its peg*", we can only understand what is being said in lexical

terms. That is, we can only imagine a lost horse returning to its peg. However, in this case, the main task of the proverb is the pragmatic purpose, namely, the hidden, warm feeling that a person, no matter where he is, should return to his homeland, to his roots, to his family, and find happiness only there, does not reach the reader at all. For a Western reader, this image remains just a simple statement about the life of domestic animals.

The main reason for this is directly related to the historical lifestyle, cultural values, and linguistic memory of the Uzbek speakers. The proverb is based on the lifestyle of our ancestors in the past - the incomparable place of the horse in human life and the philosophy of harmony with nature [Shomaqsudov, 2001:115]. For the peoples of Central Asia, the "horse" has been a symbol of loyalty, power, honor, and companionship for centuries. "Qoziq" is not just a piece of wood or iron to which a horse is tied, but also carries macro-meanings of stability, stability, shelter and a person's fulcrum in life. In the Uzbek mentality, the concept of "qoziq" is inextricably linked to the concepts of homeland, motherland and dynastic roots. Therefore, "finding a qoziq" means deep cognitive meanings such as understanding one's own identity, returning to one's place [Salomov, 1983:78].

Analysis 2: Cultural realities and communicative translation

If we analyze the proverb "*Qozonga yaqin yursang, qorasi yuqar, yomonga yaqin yursang, balosi yuqar*" (*If you are close to a cauldron, you will be in trouble, if you are close to a bad one, you will be in trouble*), which very clearly expresses the socio-moral views and life experience of the Uzbek people, the word "cauldron" in this case is not just a vessel for cooking food or a household item. In Uzbek culture, a cauldron is a unique concept and symbol of weddings, neighborhood gatherings, hospitality and mutual solidarity. In the past, food was cooked on an open fire, on wood, and naturally, the outside of the cauldron turned black. This black soot touched and stained the clothes of a person who approached it carelessly. The people skillfully transferred this simple everyday situation to human morality: being friends with ill-mannered, uneducated people "stains" a person's reputation and character, just like soot on a cauldron.

If the translator translates this profound analogy into English literally as "*If you walk close to the cauldron, its soot will smear you*", the reader will immediately experience linguistic and cultural misunderstanding. There are two reasons for this: firstly, in modern English culture, cooking food over an open fire in a large cauldron is not a common occurrence, and people cannot relate this process to their lives. Secondly, in English, the word "cauldron" is more reminiscent of a pot in which evil sorcerers boil things in fairy tales. That is, soot does not work as a metaphor for a negative object in English culture.

As the English translation expert P. Newmark noted in his research, if the image in the source language cannot evoke the same emotion in the target language, the translator should immediately look for alternative social images that are familiar to the reader [Newmark, 1988:114]. In translation theory, this method is called "communicative translation". Therefore, it is advisable to use partial alternatives of this proverb in English, which convey the same meaning, but with changed images. For example, the proverbs "*He that lies down with dogs shall rise up with fleas*" or "*A rotten apple injures its neighbors*" can be correct pragmatic equivalents. Note that the English used the images of "dog and flea" or "rotten apple" instead of the pot and black soot. Although the outer linguistic words of the text has completely changed, the main macro-meaning of the proverb has been preserved.

Analysis 3: Mental differences and the problem of untranslatability

One of the most basic concepts of the Uzbek mentality is the value of hospitality. The proverb "*Mehmon otangdek ulug'*", which is actively used in our literature and speech, fully reveals the high level of oriental values, their language and spirit and respect for the father in the Uzbek family is at the highest level. The fact that the guest is also respected at the same level as this absolute authority is the height of Uzbek grace.

Translating this meaning directly into English as "*A guest is as great as your father*" is not just a cultural misunderstanding for a foreign reader, but may seem strange and illogical in some sense. In their understanding, no matter how much respect is shown to a guest who comes to the house, the guest is still considered a "stranger" and he is never elevated above the status of the father, the pillar of the family.

According to translation theory, when the worldviews of two nations come into complete conflict, an extremely free approach is required from the translator in order to maintain the balance of meaning and national spirit. G. Salomov, one of the founders of the Uzbek school of translation studies, taught that when translating such complex national concepts, only an explanation or functional synonym should be sought [Salomov, 1983:156]. That is, it is logical to express the greatness of the guest not directly through the image of a father, but through the expression of high respect that also exists in the West in the form of "*Guests are highly respected*". If it is necessary to preserve the artistic meaning of the work, the purely English equivalent, "*A guest is a jewel on the cushion of hospitality*," is the pragmatically most appropriate choice.

Conclusion

The above scientific and practical analysis proves that the translation of linguistic units, in particular proverbs, is not limited to knowledge of the vocabulary of two languages. The English equivalents of Uzbek proverbs do not always fall into the same lexical pattern as we think. Each language has its own history, culture and psychology hidden behind the words. Translating examples of Uzbek folk oral art requires the translator not only to translate the text, but also to deeply feel the lifestyle, beliefs and culture of the source language speakers. Also, the translator must be able to culturally adapt national images, find partial equivalents and appropriately use descriptive translation methods, taking into account the mentality of the Western reader. Only then will the true power and beauty of Uzbek proverbs reach English-speaking peoples in their full and attractive form.

References:

1. Baker M. In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation. - London: Routledge, 2018. - 356 p.
2. Newmark P. A Textbook of Translation. - New York: Prentice-Hall International, 1988. - 312 p.
3. Salomov G'. Tarjima nazariyasi asoslari. - Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1983. - 230 b.
4. Shomaqsudov Sh., Shorahmedov Sh. Ma'nolar maxzani. - Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2001. - 448 b.